

IMPACT OF EMPLOYMENT SETTINGS OF PERSON WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY ON SELF DETERMINATION

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Abstract

Persons with intellectual disability who have self-determination skills have stronger chances of being successful in making the transition to adulthood including employment and independence. Suitable employment helps a person in earning respect and dignity in family and society. Persons with Intellectual disability in particular finds it more challenging due to lack of opportunities available. The current study is conducted on 120 adults with Intellectual Disability working in various employment setting i.e., Open, Supported and Sheltered Employment settings. The results revealed that Persons with Intellectual disability working in open employment settings have higher self determination followed by supported and sheltered employment settings. The study further reflects that male population has higher levels of self-determination than females.

Keywords: *Employment, Intellectual disability, Open employment, sheltered employment, supported employment, self determination, Adult*

Introduction:

Employment plays an important role in an individual's life. Adequate and appropriate placement for earning a livelihood is every individual's aim. This way an adult is expected and attain economic self reliance needed for his/her existence

While examining the relevant skills and competencies needed by special education students, particularly persons with intellectual disabilities, researchers and educators have come to realize the significance of self-determination (SD) in them.

The perception of people with intellectual disabilities as competent, able, and worthy of respect is a relatively recent occurrence; thus, it is not surprising that discussions about self-determination have, by and large, excluded consideration of its application to people with intellectual disabilities.

Employment:

Persons with intellectual disability who are given less opportunity for such employment, possess the potential to work, earn and live in the community as a respectable person and provided with necessary training, placement and support services. Owing to the mental capacities and skills of persons with ID, they could be allowed to work under different types of settings and situations to gain economic sustenance and livelihoods. They can also be trained to work in the in following types of employment settings.

Sheltered Employment

Sheltered workshops are large employment centers that provide employment and therapeutic interventions for persons with mild or moderate ID. Work is typically provided through work contracts in various areas.

Competitive/Open Employment:

Competitive/open employment has been defined as working for at least a minimum wage with co-workers without disabilities at a job that provides room for advancement in a setting that produces valued goods and services. Persons with ID have proven themselves to be successfully placed and maintained in competitive/open employment settings.

Supported Employment:

Supported employment projects were encouraged to change the way employment-related services were delivered to persons with ID (Elder, 1986). It has four components: that is, job placement, on-job training, monitoring and follow-up, and retention services, which are further divided into four types: supported work, enclave work, mobile crew and bench work.

Self Determination:

Self-determination is a concept reflecting the belief that individuals have the right to direct their own lives. Students with intellectual disability who have self-determination skills have stronger chances of being successful in making the transition to adulthood including employment and independence (Wehmeyer & Schwartz, 1997). A self-determined person sets goals, makes decisions, sees options, solves problems, speaks up for himself, understand what supports are needed for success and knows how to evaluate outcomes (Martin & Marshal, 1995).

Philosophy:

The determination of self implies the inner power of persons acting as a driving force to work and earn livelihoods. This capacity of a person in general is termed as “Karm hi dharm

hai” in “Sanatan” doctrine. The term in itself constitutes duty, that is, Kartvya.” The What, Why and How performing work are necessary for earning livelihoods as work provides an opportunity for economic self-sufficiency, fosters social connectedness to others in society, contributes to a sense of dignity and self-worth, and serves as a means of self-expression. Depending upon the level of this capacity he is supposed to perform satisfactory duty work under employment settings according to duty work under employment settings according to his choice or liking. This type of life situation provides him with the opportunity to enhance his capability for work efficiency with the required gains for earning his livelihood along with social economic status.

Hypothesis:

There will be no significant difference in the domain-wise and overall self-determination levels of the employed group placed in different types of **employment settings: open, sheltered and self-employment.**

Methodology:

Sampling:

In this study, the survey method was used to collect data from five states/UTs, that is, Chandigarh, Haryana, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, and Punjab. The sample size of 120 adults with intellectual disabilities of age above 18 years, was equally divided by gender and equally distributed in three employment settings, as detailed in Table 1.

Table : 1

Sample population showing variables in different groups and items.

Variables		Employed 120	
Employment		Male	Female
Settings	Open	20	20
	Supported	20	20
	Sheltered	20	20

Methodology:

1. Assessment of Self Determination in Employed group using Self Determination Scale for Assessment of Adults with Intellectual Disability (SDSAID)
2. Impact suitability- Employment under different workplace employment settings according to age, gender, and experience.
3. Types of employment under study: Sheltered, Open, supported, and self-employment.

Results:

Table: 2
Overall and domain wise comparison self determination levels of employed group working in open, supported, and sheltered employment settings

Overall domain wise	Emp. Setting	N	Mean	SD
Overall scores	Open	20	94.2250	10.86157
	supported	20	88.0500	9.32312
	sheltered	20	85.1000	9.49440
Personal Management(PM)	Open	20	31.40	2.405
	supported	20	30.10	2.384
	sheltered	20	29.20	2.839
Community Participation (CP)	Open	20	15.83	2.925
	supported	20	14.50	1.840
	sheltered	20	13.80	1.951
Recreation & Leisure (RL)	Open	20	12.13	3.891
	supported	20	10.80	1.786
	sheltered	20	10.58	1.880
Choice Making (CM)	Open	20	16.88	2.98
	supported	20	15.85	2.88
	sheltered	20	15.28	2.61
Problem Solving (PS)	Open	20	18	1.26
	supported	20	16.8	1.6
	sheltered	20	16.25	1.83

Table: 3
Showing results of oneway ANOVA on overall and domain wise self determination levels of employed group working in open, supported, and sheltered employment settings

Variable Self Determination	Types of Employment	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Overall	Between Groups	1734.650	2	867.325	8.819	.000
	Within Groups	11506.475	117	98.346		
	Total	13241.125	119			
	Between Groups	97.867	2	48.933	7.517	.001

Personal Management (PM)	Within Groups	761.600	117	6.509		
	Total	859.467	119			
Community Participation (CP)	Between Groups	84.617	2	42.308	8.060	.001
	Within Groups	614.175	117	5.249		
	Total	698.792	119			
Recreation Leisure (RL)	Between Groups	56.117	2	28.058	3.851	.024
	Within Groups	852.550	117	7.287		
	Total	908.667	119			
Choice Making (CM)	Between Groups	52.550	2	26.275	3.279	.041
	Within Groups	937.450	117	8.012		
	Total	990.000	119			
Problem Solving (PS)	Between Groups	64.067	2	32.033	12.752	.000
	Within Groups	293.900	117	2.512		
	Total	357.967	119			

Overall comparison of self-determination scores with respect to various employment settings of the Employed PWID group working in open, supported, and sheltered employment. The overall mean score obtained in the open employment setting was 94.22, and the standard deviation (σ -standard deviation) was 10.86. In the case of Supported E, the mean score was 88.05 and the standard deviation (σ) was 9.32. The mean score under sheltered employment was 85.1, and the deviation (σ) was 9.49. The mean differences among these three groups were tested using one-way ANOVA. The F-ratio of the overall scale is 8.81, which is significant at the 1% level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The mean scores of self determination Personal Management (PM) based on three types of employment settings were open employment 31.4 and deviation (σ) is 2.4, supported employment is 30.1 and standard deviation (σ) is 2.38 and sheltered employment is 29.2 and deviation (σ) is 2.39. The mean difference among these three groups was tested using one way ANOVA. The F-ratio of PM domain is 7.51 which were significant at 1% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Mean scores of Self Determination Community Participation (CP) based on three types of employment depicts the mean score in open employment is 15.83 and deviation (σ) is 2.92,

supported employment is 14.5 and standard deviation (σ) is 1.84 and sheltered employment is 13.8 and standard deviation (σ) is 1.95. The mean difference among these three groups was tested using one way ANOVA. The F-ratio of CP is 8.06 which is significant at 1% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Mean scores of Recreation and Leisure (RL) based on three types of employment depicts the mean score in open employment is 12.13 and standard deviation (σ) is 3.89, supported employment is 10.8 and standard deviation (σ) is 1.78 and sheltered employment is 10.58 and standard deviation (σ) is 1.88. The mean differences among these three groups were tested using one way ANOVA. The F-ratio of RL 3.85 is significant at 1% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Mean scores Choice Making (CM) based on three types of employment depicts the mean scores in open employment is 16.88 and standard deviation (σ) is 2.98, supported employment is 15.85 and standard deviation (σ) is 2.88 and sheltered employment is 15.28 and standard deviation (σ) is 2.61. The mean difference among these three groups was tested using one way ANOVA. The F-ratio of CM 3.27 which is significant at 1% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Mean scores of Problem Solving (PS) based on three types of employment depicts the mean score of open employment is 18 and standard deviation (σ) is 1.26, supported employment is 16.8 and standard deviation (σ) is 1.6 and sheltered employment is 16.25 and standard deviation (σ) is 1.83. The mean difference among these three groups was tested using one way ANOVA. The F-ratio of PS 12.75, which is significant at the 1% level, thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion:

Employment:

To be employed, a person with ID is required to achieve matching abilities traits or training so that one can meet the life requirements by earning livelihoods. Such components formed the study elements in the present study. In this context Thressiakutty and Rao (2001) explained that the most critical aspects of an individual's capacity for employment are: parental support, a friendly and social personality and a desire to work. They further suggested that IQ scores test scores or academic abilities are not necessarily important features of the successfully employed persons with ID. It is further reported that self employment of work place habilitation becomes natural process through movement in community giving sense of self esteem and responsibility. Strategies have also been advanced that help to cope up with tension during

work, deal with thoughts or adverse ideas, talking pertinent issues, avoiding childish behavior, clumsiness, calmness, restlessness, loss of temper, refuse to follow instruction and maintenance of self esteem leading him to perform well in employment. Importance of transition training from school to work in a systematic manner leads to successful job retention was also recommended by them.

As reported by Wehmeyer and Garner (2003), social contributions provided by employment to persons with intellectual disability allow them to built self image, improve wage, habit, social skill and effectiveness in their approach for earning livelihood. Later on have worked out impact feature of employment reporting that the environment in which such people live, learn and work, play an important role in improving personal characteristics including level of intelligence.

With respect to employment in sheltered environment Zeltin reported adults with intellectual disability attaining life conceptions while working in sheltered workshop in addition to gaining competence in job placement with vocational training in similar environments (Thressiakutty and Narayan (1990). Enhanced production rate at work place though intervention to person with intellectual disability has been reported by Mohanty (1994). It also goes in accordance with the present study. Thressiakutty (1994) reported that persons with intellectual disability in supported and open employment get on the job training that proved effective for their job retention.

Self Determination:

To be employed a person with ID is required to achieve matching abilities, traits or training so that he or she can meet the job requirement (Thressiakutty 2001). Practical concept of self that includes assertions, like-interests, awareness of own strength, the behaviours to achieve basic needs preference learning style and skill attributes of disabilities and leadership compounding to personality have also been forwarded in this respect. These assertions conform to present findings relating to SD and its domains.

The domains of SD were assessed keeping in view the traits of self viz. interest, awareness of own strength, behavior to achieve basic needs, preferences, learning style, skills attributes of own disabilities and leadership as reported by Thressiakutty (2001). Whether SD remains, the question mark to attain the required level to make the baseline of the present study. To this respect findings of this study indicate personal management skills were more in employed persons with ID

On Choice Making (Wehmeyer and Garner, (2016)) found opportunities provided to persons with ID contributed significantly and positively in choice making.

Whiteman (1987) proved that poor social skill is a barrier in problem solving. Problem solving and social skills overlap on a daily basis when an individual decides the course of action to meet the needs or solve a conflict or problem. PS brings social competence. (Wehmeyer and Kelchner,1993).

The reports of Wehymer and Moon (1985) with regard to community participation have similarity in the findings of the present study.

With regard to Choice Making (Nirje 1972) has given an overview that has provided confidence in many people with ID, have had neither the experience nor the opportunity to assume responsibility for basic choices and decisions that impacts their daily lives. But the findings of this study revealed many persons with employed ID got chances for choice making.

Conclusion:

The present study reflects that adults with Intellectual Disability have higher self determination who are working in open employment settings as compared to supported and sheltered employment settings as they are getting better opportunity of interaction with general population/ environment. The study further revealed that male population had higher self determination scores as compared to their female counterparts. Domain wise mean scores of adults placed in Open employment settings have higher levels of Self Determination followed by adults placed in Supported and Sheltered employment settings.

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